

Conductometric Studies of Hydrochlorides of widely used Medicinal Compounds in Mixed Solvents

S. C. DUTTA and S. C. LAHIRI*

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani, Kalyani-741 235

Manuscript received 21 November 1990, revised 21 May 1992, accepted 27 May 1992

Most of the drugs that are of common use are usually administered as hydrochlorides. The drugs are usually amphipathic in nature and expected to have similar physicochemical properties like those of tetraalkylammonium halides. The conductance data of the hydrochlorides of drugs like ephedrine, pseudoephedrine, papaverine, propranolol, metoclopramide, dicyclomine and DL-phenylpropanolamine in methanol+water and ethanol+water mixtures at 298 K have been analysed by Fuoss (1978) equation. The effects of co-solvents methanol and ethanol on ionic association and the variation of the Walden products have been examined.

The division of Λ° into single ion values using reference electrolyte Bu_4NBPh_4 , has been made. The single ion conductance values may be useful to have an approximate idea regarding drug diffusion and change in the values of hydrophobic interactions in going from water to non-aqueous solvents.

Studies on the transport properties of electrolytes in different solvents are of great importance to obtain informations on the behaviour of ions in solutions. However, most of the studies are restricted to tetraalkylammonium halides and simple electrolytes in aqueous, non-aqueous and mixed solvents^{1,2}. Most of the drugs that are of use are highly insoluble in water and they are usually administered as hydrochlorides. It has been observed that like tetraalkylammonium halides, the drugs are amphipathic in nature due to the presence of hydrophobic and hydrophilic groups in the same molecule. Therefore, it is desirable to study transport properties of these hydrochlorides from the physicochemical point of view. Moreover, these studies would enable us to derive useful informations regarding the ion-solvent interactions of the drug molecules. Ion-solvent interactions are the controlling forces in dilute solutions where ion-ion interactions are absent and these studies may be of great importance in determining the pharmacological properties of the drug molecules, a possibility not properly examined and explored. The single ion conductance values may be useful to have an approximate idea regarding drug diffusion and a change in the values of hydrophobic interactions of drug cations in going from water to non-aqueous solvents.

These considerations led us to undertake the conductometric study of the drugs like ephedrine(1a), pseudoephedrine(1b), papaverine(2), propranolol(3), dicyclomine(4), metoclopramide(5), and DL-phenylpropanolamine(6) (as hydrochlorides) conductometrically in methanol+water and ethanol+water mixtures at 298 K. The conductance studies of sodium tetraphenylborate, tetrabutylammonium chloride and sodium chloride have also been made.

These study would enable us to verify whether any appreciable ion-association exists in aqueous, methanol+water and ethanol+water mixtures. The effect of co-solvents methanol and ethanol on the hydrophobic behaviour of the hydrochlorides and the variation of the Walden product may be properly investigated from such studies. The division of Λ° into single ion value using 'reference electrolyte' method would enable us to have a relative idea about the solvation parameter or ion-solvent interactions of the molecules.

Results and Discussion

The conductance data were analysed using Shedlovsky's method³ as given by Gill⁴. Since some of these salts were found to be associated in water⁵, we, therefore, preferred to adopt the recent method of computation proposed by Fuoss⁶. For a set of conductance data ($C_j, X_j; j=1, 2, \dots, n$), three adjustable parameters Λ°, K_A and R (co-sphere diameter) can be obtained by solving appropriate equations,

$$\Lambda = \gamma [\Lambda^\circ(1 + RX) + EL] \quad (1)$$

$$\gamma = 1 - K_A C \gamma^2 f^2 \quad (2)$$

$$-\ln f = \beta K/2 (1 + KR) \quad (3)$$

$$\beta = e^2 / \epsilon kT \quad (4)$$

RX and EL are relaxation and hydrodynamic terms respectively and ϵ =relative permittivity or dielectric constant of the solvent. Expressions for RX and EL were the same as derived by Fuoss. The computation was done using a Fortran IV programme supplied by Professor Fuoss. The program was slightly modified for use with the Wipro Z-650 computer. First a coarse scan for all salts were done from $R=4$ to 15 with increment of one unit of R -value.

But no significant minimum was found and the computations were done by fixing R at $\beta/2$. The values of K_A , Δ° , β and $\sigma\% = 100\sigma/\Delta^\circ$

where

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{(\Delta_j(\text{cal}) - \Delta_j(\text{obs}))^2}{n-2} \quad (5)$$

are given in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—PROPERTIES OF MIXED SOLVENTS (ALCOHOL+WATER AT 298 K

Alcohol Wt%	Density g ml ⁻¹	Viscosity cP	Dielectric const.	Sp. cond. $\times 10^3$ Ω^{-1} cm ⁻¹	$\beta = \frac{e^2}{\epsilon kT}$ (λ)
<i>Methanol</i>					
16.0	0.971	1.33	71.42	1.31	7.84
34.4	0.943	1.562	63.69	1.17	8.80
54.2	0.906	1.490	54.34	1.04	10.30
75.9	0.855	1.082	44.44	0.87	12.60
<i>Ethanol</i>					
16.4	0.972 2	1.650	70.42	1.24	7.96
34.4	0.944 8	2.244	58.48	1.02	9.58
54.1	0.903 5	2.300	46.72	0.71	11.98
76.0	0.850 3	1.830	34.84	0.46	16.08

For most of the compounds, Δ° values are found to pass through the minimum in the region of 54–64 wt%^a of alcohols with $\Delta^\circ_{\text{methanol+water}} > \Delta^\circ_{\text{ethanol+water}}$.

The Δ° values of these hydrochlorides in water are very close to those of tetraalkylammonium chlorides indicating similarity between drug cations and tetraalkylammonium ions in aqueous solutions. But since the conductance values of the drugs in lipid (i.e. n-octanol) could not be determined, efforts may be made to have an idea of conductance values in going from water to non-aqueous solvents so that informations regarding the change in hydrophobic interactions may be obtained. However, in order to comprehend better insight regarding ion-solvent interactions or hydrophobic interactions, it is desirable to have single ion equivalent conductance values.

In absence of transference number of ions in mixed solvents, single ion values were determined using the 'reference electrolyte method'. The tetrabutylammonium tetraphenylborate (Bu_4NBPh_4), first used by Fuoss and Hirst⁷ and later by Coetzee and McGuire⁸ in non-aqueous mixed solvents,

$$\Delta^\circ_{\text{Bu}_4\text{NBPh}_4} = \Delta^\circ_{\text{Bu}_4\text{NCl}} + \Delta^\circ_{\text{NaBPh}_4} - \Delta^\circ_{\text{NaCl}} \quad (6)$$

TABLE 2—LIMITING EQUIVALENT CONDUCTANCES AND OTHER PARAMETERS OF THE DRUGS (AS HYDROCHLORIDE) IN DIFFERENT ALCOHOL+WATER MIXTURES AT 298 K*

Alcohol Wt %	Λ_0	K_A	σ %	Λ_0	K_A	σ %
Methanol						
<i>Pseudoephedrine</i>						
16.0	75.99	6.97	0.171	<i>Ephedrine</i>		
34.4	60.68	8.48	0.191	71.99	1.25	0.15
54.2	51.50	2.29	0.165	56.44	—ve	—
75.9	63.00	6.20	0.285	49.71	—ve	—
<i>Papaverine</i>						
16.0	71.72	0.02	0.17	<i>Propranolol</i>		
34.4	63.68	—ve	—	79.87	26.97	0.321
54.2	56.71	—ve	—	63.84	25.94	0.533
75.9	63.33	—ve	—	56.65	8.66	0.315
<i>Metoclopramide</i>						
16.0	65.82	5.61	0.389	<i>Dicyclomine</i>		
34.4	53.91	6.37	0.184	74.76	15.52	0.282
54.2	51.77	1.92	0.179	60.13	9.58	0.40
75.9	58.19	3.71	0.361	52.26	—ve	—
<i>DL-phenylpropranolamine</i>						
16.0	76.39	6.87	0.126			
34.4	61.53	9.90	0.174			
54.2	52.59	4.39	0.202			
75.9	64.57	9.86	0.285			
Ethanol						
<i>Pseudoephedrine</i>						
16.4	73.44	22.63	0.067	<i>Ephedrine</i>		
34.4	51.33	18.39	0.229	68.11	3.44	0.105
54.1	40.43	7.78	0.079	51.31	2.25	0.166
76.0	37.13	11.77	0.255	44.52	2.11	0.176
<i>Papaverine</i>						
16.4	62.00	—ve	—	<i>Propranolol</i>		
34.4	47.01	—ve	—	69.43	24.49	0.114
54.1	39.90	—ve	—	48.99	30.18	0.167
76.0	42.29	—ve	—	40.11	26.92	0.145
<i>Metoclopramide</i>						
16.4	59.20	19.79	0.087	<i>Dicyclomine</i>		
34.4	41.94	22.06	0.162	59.78	12.51	0.123
54.1	34.83	23.97	0.193	41.40	6.49	0.317
76.0	31.76	34.46	0.292	33.76	4.72	0.178
<i>DL-phenylpropranolamine</i>						
16.4	69.20	11.12	0.018			
34.4	49.17	13.23	0.052			
54.1	40.09	15.36	0.220			
76.0	39.35	38.35	0.549			

*Using Fuoss (1978) equation.

appeared to be the best for division and $\lambda_{\text{Bu}_4\text{N}^+}^0 / \lambda_{\text{BPh}_4^-}^0 = 1.07$ has been used for division^{9,10}. The values are recorded in Table 3. It is to be noted that λ_i^0 values of ions in water determined using the 'reference electrolyte' method come out to be very close (within 0.5%) to those obtained using transference number measurement. Thus, the values of λ_i^0 in mixed solvents can be regarded to be accurate within $\pm 1\%$.

The single ion conductance values are of importance as they give idea regarding the diffusion of drug cations through the different solvent media as

TABLE 3—LIMITING ION CONDUCTANCE VALUES (λ_i^0) IN DIFFERENT ALCOHOL+WATER MIXTURES AT 298 K

(a) <i>Alcohol = Methanol</i>						
Alcohol Wt %	Na^+	Cl^-	Bu_4N^+	BPh_4^-	Cations of Pseudo-Ephedrine	
16.0	41.77	56.37	15.67	14.75	19.62	15.62
34.4	32.48	42.09	16.55	15.57	8.59	14.35
54.2	33.59	38.76	16.81	15.81	12.74	10.95
75.9	39.50	39.21	27.05	25.44	23.79	18.50
<i>Papa-verine</i> <i>Propra-nalol</i> <i>Metoclo-pramide</i> <i>Dicyclo-amine</i> <i>DL-phenyl-propranolamine</i>						
16.0	15.35	23.50	9.45	18.39	20.02	
34.4	21.58	21.75	11.82	18.04	19.44	
54.2	17.95	17.89	13.01	13.50	17.83	
75.9	24.11	24.24	18.98	16.10	25.36	
(b) <i>Alcohol = Ethanol</i>						
Alcohol Wt %	Na^+	Cl^-	Bu_4N^+	BPh_4^-	Cations of Pseudo-Ephedrine	
16.4	36.20	52.66	12.29	11.55	20.78	15.45
34.4	30.04	45.29	5.53	5.20	8.04	6.02
54.1	20.65	34.05	11.25	10.58	6.38	10.47
76.0	20.02	26.52	13.28	12.50	10.61	18.11
<i>Papa-verine</i> <i>Propra-nalol</i> <i>Metoclo-pramide</i> <i>Dicyclo-amine</i> <i>DL-Phenyl-propranolamine</i>						
16.4	9.34	16.77	6.54	7.12	16.54	
34.4	1.72	3.70	0.23	0.85	3.88	
54.1	5.85	6.06	0.78	1.94	6.04	
76.0	15.37	9.58	5.24	7.93	12.83	

$$\Lambda^0 = \frac{Z^2 e F}{kT} (D_+ + D_-) \quad (7)$$

where D_+ and D_- are the diffusion coefficients of the cations and anions. The single ion conductance values of cations (except for Na^+) in general decrease and pass through minima at 54 wt% methanol and 34 wt% of ethanol.

Similar minima are also observed when Walden products $\Lambda^0 \eta_0$ or $\lambda_i^0 \eta_0$ are plotted against solvent composition (Figs. 1–4). The variations of $\Lambda^0 \eta_0$ values though similar in nature in $\text{MeOH} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{EtOH} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ mixtures but are markedly different $\lambda_i^0 \eta_0$.

Both drug molecules and alcohol molecules are characterised by the presence of hydrophobic and hydrophilic centres leading to two different types of hydration. Both compete for water structure organisation. However, specific solvation effects and hydrophobic effects act in the opposite direction¹¹. The increase in size of hydrophobic group shifts the point of maximum structure formation towards media richer in water. The minima in the viscosity-composition curves for methanol+water and ethanol+water mixtures are observed in the region of 40 wt%¹² and the maxima in viscosity almost coincide with the observed minima in Λ^0 values of the salts though the Walden products have been found to be different.

The assumption that the dielectric constant is not involved² in affecting Λ^0 values since the ionisation would be complete at infinite dilution appears to be untenable as the change in Λ^0 values is not due to the change in the number of ions but due to the difference in mobility and the resistance to the

Fig. 1. Curves : (1) compound 3, (2) 1b, (3) 2, (4) 1a, (5) 5, (6) 6 and (7) 4.

flow of ions through the solvent media. The cations and anions move in the opposite directions and the attractive forces of the oppositely charged ions will increase with decrease in dielectric constant of the solvent medium. The mobility of the ions would depend inversely on some powers of the dielectric constant.

Fig. 2. Curves : (1) compound 5, (2) 4, (3) 3, (4) 1b, (5) 6, (6) 2 and (7) 1a.

Among other factors, the equivalent conductance of an ion at infinite dilution is likely to depend on (i) solvation of ions, (ii) flow of ions through the

holes under the influence of electric field. The flow is likely to be determined by the energy required to occupy the volume of the hole into which the ion jumps plus that required to break the bonds with other molecules, and (iii) the dielectric constant of the solvent determining the ionising capability of the solvent.

Fig. 3. Curves : (1) compound 1b, (2) 1a, (3) 3, (4) 5, (5) 2, (6) 4 and (7) 6.

Fig. 4. Curves : (1) compound 1b, (2) 1a, (3) 2, (4) 5, (5) 3, (6) 6 and (7) 4.

It is expected that cations are preferentially hydrated in water and hydration is initially reinforced by the addition of alcohol leading to gradual decrease in conductance values of cations. The increased values of λ_{\pm}° in water may be due to greater freedom of ions to move through the polar hydrogen bonded solvent system having high dielectric constant. The three-dimensional water structures have 'holes' through which the transference of ions can occur rather easily. The making or breaking of solvated chains are quick enough to have a rapid transference of ions through water. The holes will be filled up gradually by the addition of alcohol molecules offering resistance to the flow of ions. However, gradual dehydration of ions takes place

after structure-formation maxima are reached leading to increased values.

It is apparent that λ_{\pm}° values and hence diffusion of the drug cations in water and aqueous binary mixtures are in the order DL-phenylpropanolamine \approx pseudoephedrine $>$ papaverine \approx ephedrine $>$ propranolol $>$ metoclopramide $>$ dicyclomine, which means that the size of the solvated ions are in the opposite order.

The quantitative explanations for the variation of Walden product with solvent composition are yet unknown, though several attempts have been made to derive a single satisfactory expression taking into account all types of ion-solvent interactions^{2,13}. However, ion-solvent interaction is specific for the ion and the solvent.

It can be assumed that the selective solvation and the nature of exchange of ions with their solvent molecules are of importance to determine the variation of λ_{\pm}° and $\lambda_{\pm}^{\circ} \eta_{\pm}$. The variation of λ_{\pm}° of the cations obviously implies a change in effective radii of ions arising from the differences in ion-solvent interactions. However, r -value of Bu_4N^+ obtained by us or by Robinson and Stokes is 4.66 or 4.77 Å in water where considerable hydration is expected. But the r -value of Bu_4N^+ determined from conductometric measurements in non-aqueous aprotic solvents where hydration effects are eliminated is 5.00 Å^{4,10} or 3.85 Å⁹. Thus considerable inconsistency is apparent and no attempt has been made to calculate the solvation number of the drug cations in the solvent mixtures.

Most of the electrolytes (except pseudoephedrine) studied can be regarded to be associated considerably (as $K_A > 10$) in aqueous solutions. It may be assumed that a fraction of these drug molecules may penetrate the lipid membrane as such and exert physiological action. The property may be utilised to correlate the physicochemical and pharmacological properties.

The association behaviour is found to change in mixed solvents though higher values of the association constants have been found at higher percentages of organic solvents in few cases and it is expected due to lowering of dielectric constant of the solvent mixtures. However, proper correlation between the association constant and the variation of dielectric constants or the distance of closest approach of ions cannot be made. Systematic studies on the transport properties of the drug molecules may provide better insight in understanding the ion-solvent interaction and the pharmacologic properties of the drug molecules.

Experimental

The drugs ephedrine hydrochloride, papaverine hydrochloride, metoclopramide hydrochloride and DL-phenylpropanolamine hydrochloride were purified

from ethanol+water mixtures, while pseudoephedrine hydrochloride, propranolol hydrochloride and dicyclomine hydrochloride were purified from ethanol, n-propanol and butanone respectively.

Guaranteed quality NaBPh_4 , Bu_4NCl (Fluka) and NaCl (G.R., E. Merck) were used as such. Methanol (G.R., E. Merck) was double-distilled and the middle fraction of the distillate was used. Ethanol (absolute; B.C.P.W., Calcutta) was treated with sufficient quantity of preheated CaO , kept overnight and distilled. The distillate was refluxed with Na-metal and redistilled, and the middle fraction was utilised. Triple-distilled water was used for conductivity measurements.

The conductance values of the compounds at different concentrations (10^{-2} – $10^{-3}M$) were taken in water, methanol+water (16.0, 34.4, 54.2 and 75.9 wt% of methanol) and ethanol+water (16.4, 34.4, 54.1 and 76 wt% of ethanol) mixtures. The physical properties of the mixed solvents are recorded in Table 1. Conductance measurements of the drugs as well as other salts were taken with a Leeds Northrup 4959 conductance bridge with a sensitivity of $\pm 0.1\%$. A 50 cycle signal was employed. A Philips conductance cell was fitted into a double-walled corning vessel containing the experimental solution. The terminals of the electrodes were kept far apart and electrode leads were removed from the experimental vessel containing the solutions in order to eliminate the error as far as possible. Cell constant was determined in the way used by Jones and Bradshaw¹⁴. The measurements were done at 298 ± 0.01 K.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (S.C.D.) thanks C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for a research scholarship. The authors express their gratitude to Mr. B. Mondal, Central Drug Laboratory, Calcutta, for supplying the samples.

References

1. D. F. EVANS and R. L. KAY, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, 70, 366; D. E. ARRINGTON and E. GRISWALD, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1970, 74, 123.
2. L. BAHADUR and M. V. RAMANAMURTI, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. I*, 1980, 1409; *Can. J. Chem.*, 1984, 62, 1051 and references cited therein.
3. T. SHEDLOVSKY, *J. Franklin Inst.*, 1938, 255, 739.
4. D. S. GILL, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. I*, 1981, 77, 751; *Electrochim. Acta*, 1979, 24, 701.
5. S. C. DUTTA, S. DAS and S. C. LAHIRI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1990, 67, 466.
6. R. M. FUOSS, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. (U.S.A.)*, 1978, 75, 16; *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1978, 82, 2427.
7. R. M. FUOSS and E. HIRST, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 82, 1013.
8. J. F. COETZEE and D. K. MCGUIRE, *J. Phys. [Chem.]*, 1963, 67, 1810.
9. S. DAS and D. K. HAZRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1988, 27, 1073.

10. D. DASGUPTA, S. DAS and D. K. HAZRA *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1988, 1057.
11. N. DOLLET and J. JUILLARD, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1976, 5, 77; Y. POINTUD and J. JUILLARD, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1977, 1907.
12. "Physical Chemistry of Organic Solvent Systems", eds. A. K. COVINGTON and T. DICKINSON, Plenum, London, 1973.
13. M. V. RAMANAMURTI and L. BAHADUR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, 14, 1015; *Electrochim. Acta*, 1980, 25, 607; R. ZWANZIG, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1963, 38, 1603; 1970, 52, 3625; P. HEMMES, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1974, 78, 907; R. A. ROBINSON and R. H. STOKES, "Electrolytic Solutions", Butterworths, London, 1959.
14. G. JONES and B. C. BRADSHAW, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 1780.